

Kinetics of the Catalytic Oxidation of Arsenious Acid with Ferric Chloride in Presence of Potassium Iodide.

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The reaction between ferric chloride and arsenious acid has been studied by Jellineck and Winogradoff (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1924, 30, 477). They found that the reaction is immeasurably slow at ordinary temperature and indeed a mixture of the two may be kept at ordinary temperature for months together without any apparent change. They, therefore, studied the reaction at two temperatures 107° and 127° by heating the reacting mixtures in sealed tubes and analysing the reaction products by a very laborious and round-about quantitative process in absence of any easy and exact volumetric method for determining the ferrous salt in the presence of arsenious acid. They found that under the conditions of the experiment, the order of the reaction is approximately trimolecular and reversible as follows:—

The present investigation was undertaken with a view, firstly, to find whether with the addition of a suitable catalyst, the reaction may be made to proceed with a measurable velocity at ordinary or any conveniently lower temperature, and secondly, to find out an easier volumetric method for following the reaction and studying the equilibrium conditions. Both of these were achieved after a few initial trials and experiments and the results obtained will be set out in the following pages.

It was observed that traces of potassium iodide strongly catalyse the reaction which proceeds with measurable velocity at ordinary temperatures (25°-30°) though the final equilibrium is attained very slowly at the end of days. The reaction was, therefore, more conveniently studied at 50° and 60° at which the final equilibrium is attained within 10 to 12 hours.

Next in our search for a suitable oxidising reagent for estimating volumetrically the ferrous salt in presence of both ferric salt and arsenious acid, it was found that ceric sulphate in sulphuric acid solution with diphenylamine hydrochloride as an internal indicator answers the purpose very well. Willard and Young (*J. Amer.*

Chem. Soc., 1928, 50, 1335) have shown the use of ceric sulphate as an oxidising volumetric reagent and their method with some modifications was used for this purpose.

Outline of the Process.

The following solutions were used for the experiments—

(a) An approximately 0.320*N* solution of ferric chloride in 0.05 *N*-HCl solution.

(b) An almost saturated solution of solid arsenious acid in water, the strength of the solution being 0.3254*N* approximately at 30°.

(c) An *N*/100 solution of pure potassium iodide in water. Different quantities of which were used as catalyser.

(d) A dilute solution of ceric sulphate (approximately *N*/100) in *N*-sulphuric acid was used as the volumetric oxidising reagent.

(e) A solution of glacial phosphoric acid (*d.* 1.7) in the proportion of 150 c.c. per litre.

(f) A dilute solution of diphenylamine hydrochloride in sulphuric acid in the proportion of 1 gm. of the amine salt in 100 c.c. of sulphuric acid (*d.* 1.84). A drop or two of this solution was used as an internal indicator for finding the end-point in the titrations.

(g) A saturated solution of silver sulphate.

For equilibrium experiments, definite volumes of arsenious acid, ferric chloride, potassium iodide and hydrochloric acid solutions were mixed in glass bottles with ground-glass stoppers and kept in the thermostat, the temperature of which was maintained constant within $\pm 1^\circ$. After 10 to 12 hours, 5 c.c. of the equilibrium mixture were taken out and poured into 50 c.c. of ice-cold freshly boiled distilled water. 10 C.c. of saturated silver sulphate solution were added to precipitate the iodide completely. 5 C.c. of phosphoric acid were then added and two drops of the diphenylamine indicator. The end point is quite sharp and is indicated by the appearance of a persistent bluish-violet coloration with a drop of a *N*/100-ceric sulphate solution. For kinetic measurements the solutions of all the reacting substances were kept in glass stoppered bottles in the thermostat till they attained the temperature of the bath. Definite volumes of the solutions were then measured out into the reacting vessel and last of all 1 or 2 c.c. of potassium iodide solution, the catalyser, was added. The reaction was followed by taking out 5 c.c. of the mixture from time to time and titrating with ceric sulphate solution as described above. Air-free conductivity water was used in all these experiments.

Equilibrium Experiments.

TABLE I.

Temperature = 50°. Concentration of the catalyst = 0.0015N.

$$K = \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{AsO}_3] \times [\text{FeCl}_2]^2}{[\text{H}_3\text{AsO}_4] \times [\text{FeCl}_2]^3 \times [\text{HCl}]^2}$$

Initial concentration of the solution in gm. mol. per litre. Equilibrium concentration of the solution in gm. mols. per litre.

Expt.	H ₃ AsO ₃	FeCl ₂	HCl	H ₃ AsO ₄	FeCl ₂	H ₃ AsO ₃	H ₃ AsO ₄	FeCl ₂	HCl	K.
1.	2.325 × 10 ⁻³	4.65 × 10 ⁻³	0.340	1.26 × 10 ⁻³	2.5 × 10 ⁻³	2.3 × 10 ⁻³	4.4 × 11 ⁻³	0.384	1.24 × 10 ⁻³	
2.	"	"	0.648	1.75 × 10 ⁻³	3.5 × 10 ⁻³	2.15 × 10 ⁻³	4.3 × 10 ⁻³	0.686	1.30 × 10 ⁻³	
3.	"	"	1.248	2.75 × 10 ⁻³	5.5 × 10 ⁻³	2.05 × 10 ⁻³	4.1 × 10 ⁻³	1.384	1.47 × 10 ⁻³	
4.	"	"	2.418	4.15 × 10 ⁻³	8.3 × 10 ⁻³	1.91 × 10 ⁻³	3.82 × 10 ⁻³	2.456	1.70 × 10 ⁻³	
5.	"	"	3.607	4.80 × 10 ⁻³	9.6 × 10 ⁻³	1.345 × 10 ⁻³	3.68 × 10 ⁻³	3.644	1.84 × 10 ⁻³	
6.	3.755 × 10 ⁻³	1.2 × 10 ⁻¹	2.678	1.05 × 10 ⁻³	4.7 × 10 ⁻³	9.65 × 10 ⁻³	7.30 × 10 ⁻³	2.746	1.58 × 10 ⁻³	
7.	"	"	3.582	1.45 × 10 ⁻³	4.78 × 10 ⁻³	3.61 × 10 ⁻³	7.23 × 10 ⁻³	3.654	1.32 × 10 ⁻³	
									Mean	1.49 × 10 ⁻³

TABLE II.

Temperature = 60°.

1.	2.325 × 10 ⁻³	4.65 × 10 ⁻³	0.648	2.26 × 10 ⁻³	4.5 × 10 ⁻³	2.1 × 10 ⁻³	4.2 × 10 ⁻³	0.684	2.60 × 10 ⁻³	
2.	"	"	2.418	4.70 × 10 ⁻³	9.4 × 10 ⁻³	1.85 × 10 ⁻³	3.71 × 10 ⁻³	2.452	2.71 × 10 ⁻³	
3.	3.755 × 10 ⁻³	1.2 × 10 ⁻¹	2.978	1.70 × 10 ⁻³	4.83 × 10 ⁻³	3.685 × 10 ⁻³	7.17 × 10 ⁻³	2.744	2.85 × 10 ⁻³	
4.	"	"	3.582	2.4 × 10 ⁻³	4.97 × 10 ⁻³	3.515 × 10 ⁻³	7.03 × 10 ⁻³	3.652	2.65 × 10 ⁻³	
									Mean	2.66 × 10 ⁻³

Heat of the reaction.—According to vant Hoff's equation for the reaction isochore, we have, $\frac{d \log K}{dT} = \frac{-Q}{RT^2}$ which on integration

gives $\log_e K_1 - \log_e K_2 = \frac{Q}{R} \times \left[\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right]$. Substituting the values of

K_1 and K_2 for 60° and 50° , we have $\log 0.00268 - \log 0.00142 =$

$$\frac{Q}{4.58} \left(\frac{1}{333} - \frac{1}{323} \right) \text{ or } Q = -13600 \text{ calories.}$$

This shows that the heat of the reaction is considerable and 13600 calories are evolved when 1 gm. mol. of arsenious acid is oxidised by 2 gm. mols. of ferric chloride with the formation of 1 gm. mol. of arsenic acid, 2 gm. mols. of ferrous chloride and 2 gm. mols. of hydrochloric acid. Jellineck and Winogradoff (*loc. cit.*) found this value to be about 18000 calories. But in view of the inaccurate and complicated methods they adopted in their analysis, we assume that our data are more accurate than theirs.

Kinetic Measurements.—The following measurements were done to determine the order of the reaction with respect to arsenious acid and ferric chloride separately.

TABLE III.

Temperature = 50° .
 $\text{FeCl}_3 = 0.03N. \text{H}_3\text{AsO}_3 = 0.242N. \text{HCl} = 0.02N. \text{KI} = 0.0007N.$

Time in mins.	x .	$a-x$.	k (monomolecular).
0	0	0.030	—
7	0.0047	0.0253	0.88
14	0.0083	0.0217	0.91
24	0.0116	0.0184	0.87
34	0.0140	0.0160	0.86
54	0.0175	0.0125	0.86
122	0.0228	0.0072	0.90

TABLE IV.

Temperature = 50°.

$H_3AsO_3 = 0.0488N$. $FeCl_3 = 0.197N$. $HCl = 0.05N$. $KI = 0.0007N$.

Time in mins.	$a-x$.	$\log \frac{a}{a-x}$.	k (bimolecular).
0	0.0488	—	—
7	0.0328	0.1703	5.7×10^{-3}
14	0.0210	0.3660	6.0×10^{-3}
24	0.0120	0.5798	5.6×10^{-3}
34	0.0078	0.7965	5.4×10^{-3}
70	0.00187	1.5502	5.1×10^{-3}

It will appear evident that the reaction is bimolecular with respect to ferric chloride and monomolecular with respect to arsenious acid. The constants obtained in Tables III and IV are fairly good.

The following experiments were then carried out to see how far the equation for a trimolecular reaction holds good and also to observe the influence of different concentrations of the catalyst on the reaction velocity. For a trimolecular reaction, we have

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \frac{x(2a-x)}{2a^2(a-x)^2}$$

TABLE V.

Concentration of all the reacting substances are taken in gm. equivalents per litre.

$H_3AsO_3 = 0.0474N$. $FeCl_3 = 0.0474N$. $HCl = 0.015N$. $KI = 0.003N$.

Temperature = 50°.

Time in mins.	x .	$2a-x$.	$(a-x)^2$.	k (trimolecular).
0	0	9.48×10^{-2}	2.95×10^{-3}	—
7	1.75×10^{-2}	7.75×10^{-2}	9.0×10^{-4}	47.98
14	2.38×10^{-2}	7.15×10^{-2}	5.58×10^{-4}	45.72
24	2.70×10^{-2}	6.78×10^{-2}	4.16×10^{-4}	40.89
54	3.24×10^{-2}	6.24×10^{-2}	2.25×10^{-4}	36.98

The effect of varying concentrations of the catalyst and also of hydrochloric acid was next studied. It was found that the velocity

of the reaction is not directly proportional to the concentration but to a higher power of the concentration of the catalyst. The concentrations of the catalyst in our experiments were varied from 0.008N to 0.00075N whereas the value of k fall from 49.98 to 9.27. It was found that the concentration of hydrochloric acid has not a marked effect on the velocity of the reaction which falls off by 30% only whereas the concentration of HCl increased from 0.63N to 3.52N. The temperature coefficient for 10° between 50° and 60° was found to be 1.9 approximately. It is also significant that the velocity constant falls off by about 25% (compare Table V) for which we have attempted to offer an explanation later on.

Discussion.

The velocity of oxidation of arsenious acid by ferric chloride in aqueous solution proceeds with negligibly small velocity at 50°. But if potassium iodide is added then the velocity increases enormously. It appears probable that this reaction is really made up of the following two consecutive reactions:—

A similar reaction has been studied by Price (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1998, 27, 476) and Federlin (*ibid.*, 1902, 41, 565). It consists in the oxidation of phosphorus acid by potassium persulphate with hydriodic acid as catalyst. The velocities of the following reactions,

have been studied separately and it has been shown conclusively that the velocity of the complete reaction can be calculated from the velocities of the two consecutive reactions.

In this particular case however the velocity of the first reaction *i.e.*, the oxidation of iodine ion by ferric ion has a fairly large value (Sasaki, *Mm. Coll. Sci. Kyoto Imp. Univ.*, 1922, 5, 315). We would therefore expect that the observed velocity constant of the complete reaction is really the velocity of the second reaction, *i.e.*, the oxidation of arsenious acid by iodine. This reaction has been studied by Roebuck (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1902, 6, 365; 1905, 9, 727) who finds the

velocity constant to be 0.185 at 0° and the coefficient for a temperature interval of 10° is 3.39. On this basis the velocity constant at 50° will be 61.42. This value is of the same order of magnitude as those recorded in this paper.

It now remains to account for our experimental observation that the complete reaction is bimolecular with respect to ferric ion and monomolecular with respect to arsenious acid. The reaction between a ferric salt and an iodide is really a reversible one

and if equilibrium is attained fairly quickly, the concentration of iodine is

$$[\text{I}_2] = K \cdot \frac{[\text{Fe}^{+++}]^2 [\text{I}^-]^2}{[\text{Fe}^{++}]^2}$$

This equilibrium constant is very sensitive to the intensity of illumination, the quantity of free iodine in equilibrium rapidly diminishing as the intensity of illumination is increased (Sasaki, *loc. cit.*; Rideal and Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 416; Kistiakowsky, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 976). We may assume that in diffused sunlight in which the experiments were carried out, the concentration of I-ion is not far different from the concentration of potassium iodide added to the solution. Hence the concentration of free iodine is proportional to the square of the concentration of the ferric salt and inversely proportional to the square of the concentration of the ferrous salt.

At the beginning of the experiment the velocity of the second reaction will be proportional to the square of the concentration of ferric salt and to the concentration of arsenious acid. This has been actually found to be the case. But with the progress of the reaction as the concentration of ferrous ion increases, the equilibrium concentration of iodine will diminish and the trimolecular velocity constant will diminish in magnitude. This has also been found to be the case.

In conclusion, I should express my deep gratitude to Professor J. C. Ghosh at whose suggestion this investigation was undertaken and who took a keen interest during the progress of the work.

